

Supporting Information

Two-dimensional vanadium sulfide flexible graphite/polymer films for near-infrared photoelectrocatalysis and electrochemical energy storage

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Evaluation of the electrochemically active surface area

Electrochemically active surface area (ECSA) [cm^2] evaluated from the double layer capacitance, C_{DL} in a non-faradaic region of the CV measurement is described by Equation S1.[1,2]

$$\text{ECSA} = \frac{C_{DL}}{C_s} \quad (\text{S1})$$

where C_s is the specific capacitance of the electrode or the capacitance of a smooth planar surface of the same material measured under the identical electrolyte conditions. A glassy carbon electrode (SE 101, CH Instruments Inc.) was used to determine the C_s as $22.7 \mu\text{F cm}^{-2}$, which is comparable to the C_s values in the literature.[2] It should be noted that graphite/PLA film in this work clearly contains PLA, yet there is no perfectly flat graphite/PLA surface as a reference, hence, glassy carbon consists of purely carbon is adapted.

Based on the cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves at different scan rates shown in Fig. S2A, B, the anodic and cathodic current (density) at the mid-point of the potential window of each curve is extracted and plotted against the scan rate in Fig. S2C. The linear fitting of the plot provides the slope as C_{DL} . [2] Taking into consideration both anodic and cathodic current (density), the average C_{DL} of blank graphite and 2.5 wt% VS_x/graphite film is 9.1 and 16.8 mF, respectively. This leads to the ECSA of 405.9 and 721.7 cm^2 , respectively.

Calculation of areal capacitance, areal capacity, energy density, and power density

In a three-electrode system, the areal capacitance of an electrode, $C_{\text{electrode}}$ [mF cm^{-2}] is calculated from the CV curves, given by Equation S2.

$$C_{\text{electrode}} = \frac{\int_{V_1}^{V_2} I(V) dV}{v (V_2 - V_1) A} \times 1000 \quad (\text{S2})$$

The areal capacity, $Q_{\text{electrode}}$ [mAh cm^{-2}] of an electrode is calculated from the CV analysis using Equation S3.

$$Q_{\text{electrode}} = \frac{\int_{V_1}^{V_2} I(V) dV}{v A} \times \frac{1000}{3600} \quad (\text{S3})$$

where $I(V)$ is the cathodic current [mA] of the CV loop, v is the scan rate [mV s^{-1}], A is the active geometrical area of the electrode [cm^2], and V_1 and V_2 are the potential limits for the CV measurement.

In a two-electrode system, the areal capacitance of the cell, C_{cell} [mF cm^{-2}] and areal capacity, Q_{cell} [mAh cm^{-2}] are calculated according to Equation S2 and S3, respectively. Further, C_{cell} [mF cm^{-2}] and Q_{cell} [mAh cm^{-2}] can be calculated from the constant current discharging curve of galvanostatic charge-discharge (GCD) measurement, described by Equation S4 and S5, respectively:

$$C_{\text{cell}} = \frac{I \Delta t_d}{\Delta V A} \quad (\text{S4})$$

$$Q = \frac{I \times \Delta t_d}{A} \times \frac{1}{3600} \quad (\text{S5})$$

where I is the constant discharge current [mA], Δt_d is the total discharging time [s], ΔV is the range of discharge voltage [V] and A is the geometrical area of the cell [cm^2].

The obtained C_{cell} [mF cm^{-2}] is applied in Equation S6 for the calculation of areal energy density, E_{cell} [$\mu\text{Wh cm}^{-2}$], which is subsequently used in Equation S7 for the calculation of power density, P_{cell} [$\mu\text{W cm}^{-2}$].

$$E_{\text{cell}} = 0.5 \times C_{\text{cell}} \times \Delta V^2 \times \frac{1000}{3600} \quad (\text{S6})$$

$$P_{\text{cell}} = \frac{E_{\text{cell}}}{t_d} \times 3600 \quad (\text{S7})$$

where t_d [s] is the discharge time.

Calculation of real and imaginary part of capacitances for Bode plot

In the Bode plot from EIS measurement, the real part and imaginary part of the capacitances are calculated from Equation S8a,b. [3]

$$C'(\omega) = \frac{-Z''(\omega)}{\omega |Z(\omega)|^2} \quad (\text{S8a})$$

$$C''(\omega) = \frac{Z'(\omega)}{\omega |Z(\omega)|^2} \quad (\text{S8b})$$

where $C'(\omega)$ is the real part of capacitance $C(\omega)$, and $C''(\omega)$ is the imaginary part of capacitance $C(\omega)$, and $Z'(\omega)$ and $Z''(\omega)$ are the real and imaginary part of impedance $Z(\omega)$, respectively. ω is the angular frequency, $\omega = 2\pi f$, and f is the frequency [Hz].

Evaluation of the ionic conductivity of the gel electrolyte in the solid-state supercapacitor cell

The ionic conductivity, σ [S m^{-1}] is calculated following Equation S9.[4]

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{R_b} \frac{L}{A} \quad (\text{S9})$$

where R_b [Ω] is the bulk resistance obtained from the EIS spectrum, L [cm] is the distance between the two pieces of stainless-steel electrode, equivalent to the thickness of the electrolyte, and A [cm^2] is the contact area of the electrolyte with stainless-steel.

Fig. S1. CV measurement at different scan rates for the evaluation of double layer capacitance, C_{DL} for A) blank and B) 2.5 wt% VS_x /graphite film. C) Plot of current density at mid-point from the potential window in (A, B) against scan rate for the determination of C_{DL} from the slope of the plot.

Fig. S2. Brunauer-Emmett-Teller nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm of VS_x /graphite film.

Fig. S3. A, B) SEM images of cross-section view of the as-prepared graphite film (mass ratio of PLA:graphite is 1:2) and the evaluation of the film thickness. C, D) STEM images of the exfoliated VS_x layers and the dotted lines trace the different VS_x layers.

Fig. S4. SEM-EDX spectroscopy elemental mapping of the exfoliated VS_x . A) SEM image of the area for mapping, B) overlay of all elemental maps, individual EDX map of C–F) vanadium, sulfur, carbon, and oxygen. All scale bars are 500 nm.

Fig. S5. XPS survey spectrum of the exfoliated VS_x and the distribution of the major elements in atomic percentage.

Fig. S6. A) LSV of HER of blank (as reference) and 1 – 5 wt% VS_x /graphite films with and without activation, measured at the scan rate of 2 mV s^{-1} . B) Chronoamperometry profile of 2.5 wt% VS_x /graphite film with an applied potential of $\approx -0.45 V_{RHE}$ for 20 h. Electrolyte: 0.5 M H_2SO_4 .

Fig. S7. Optical absorbance spectrum of VS_x suspension.

Fig. S8. SEM images of 2.5 wt% VS_x /graphite A) before and B) after long hour chronoamperometry measurement in Fig. S6B.

Fig. S9. XPS of high-resolution core-level spectra of O 1s, V 2p, and S 2p for 2.5 wt% VS_x/graphite film after long hour chronoamperometry measurement in Fig. S6B.

Table S1. Comparison of VS_x in electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction.

Material	Synthesis technique	Electrode/substrate	Overpotential vs. RHE at -10 mA cm^{-2}	Ref.
VS ₂ nanoplates	Hydrothermal	Carbon paper	$\approx 42 \text{ mV}$	[5]
VS ₂	Metal-chalcogen combustion	Glassy carbon	$\approx 1000 \text{ mV}$	[6]
Bulk VS ₂	Metal-chalcogen combustion	Glassy carbon	$\approx 1100 \text{ mV}$	[7]
Exfoliated VS ₂	Metal-chalcogen combustion	Glassy carbon	$\approx 950 \text{ mV}$	[7]
Defect-rich VS ₂ nanosheets	Solvothermal; hydrothermal	Glassy carbon	$\approx 43 \text{ mV}$; $\approx 47 \text{ mV}$	[8]
1T-VS ₂ nanosheets	Chemical vapor deposition	Glassy carbon	$\approx 68 \text{ mV}$	[9]
VS ₂ ; VS ₂ /rGO	Hydrothermal	Glassy carbon	$\approx 600 \text{ mV}$ at -2 mA cm^{-2} $\approx 500 \text{ mV}$ at -6 mA cm^{-2}	[10]
VS ₂ nanoflowers	Hydrothermal	Glassy carbon	$\approx 58 \text{ mV}$	[11]
VS ₂ ; VS ₄ /rGO	Hydrothermal	Glassy carbon	$\approx 41 \text{ mV}^*$; $\approx 210 \text{ mV}^*$	[12]
VS _x /graphite-PLA flexible film	Metal-chalcogen combustion	Self-standing (no external substrate required)	$\approx 532 \text{ mV}$	This work

Note: All measurements were carried out in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ electrolyte except for the work marked with asterisk (*) was 0.1 M H₂SO₄.

Table S2. Comparison of VS_x/graphite-PLA flexible film in photo-electrocatalytic activities.

Material	Synthesis technique	Electrode/substrate	Electrolyte	Overpotential vs. RHE	Active region	Ref.
MoS ₂	Atomic layer deposition	3D carbon	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	≈440 mV at -10 mA cm ⁻²	UV and visible	[13]
MoS ₂	Composite filament processing	3D MoS ₂ -carbon	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	≈450 mV at -10 mA cm ⁻²	UV and visible	[14]
1T@2H-MoS ₂	Phase engineering of exfo-MoS ₂	FTO	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄	≈900 mV at -5 mA cm ⁻²	Visible	[15]
SnS	RF sputtered film	FTO	0.1 M HCl	≈400 mV at -6 mA cm ⁻²	UV, visible and NIR	[16]
CuInS ₂	Solvothermal transformation of Cu ₂ O to CuInS ₂	Mo/FTO	0.5 M Na ₂ SO ₄ + 0.1 M KH ₂ PO ₄	≈300 mV at -3.5 mA cm ⁻²	UV, visible and NIR	[17]
Sb ₂ Se ₃	Spin coating	Au/FTO	0.1 M H ₂ SO ₄	≈200 mV at 10 mA cm ⁻²	UV, visible and NIR	[18]
VS _x /graphite-PLA flexible film	Metal-chalcogen combustion	Self-standing (no external substrate required)	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	≈493 mV ≈503 mV at -10 mA cm ⁻²	Visible; NIR	This work

Fig. S10. Cyclic voltammetry (CV) curves of A) 1 wt% and B) 5 wt% VS_x/graphite film at different scan rates from 10 – 100 mV s⁻¹.

Separation of the charge stored into surface-controlled capacitive process, $k_1\nu$ and diffusion-controlled pseudocapacitive process, $k_2\nu^{1/2}$ at different scan rates

To obtain the k_1 and k_2 values based on Equation 5 and 6 following Dunn's method,[19,20] the current (as a function of potential), $I(V)$ was chosen for several potential points in the potential window of 0 – 1 V at the scan rate, ν of 10, 25, 50, 75 and 100 mV s^{-1} . The k_1 (slope) and k_2 (intercept) were determined from each selected potential followed by the corresponding capacitive current, $k_1\nu$. The k_1 (slope) at different potential points for both anodic and cathodic sweeps are provided in Table S3. The capacitive current, $k_1\nu$ against potential, V provides the surface controlled capacitive area as shown in the colored area in Fig. S11 for scan rates of 10 – 75 mV s^{-1} . The plot of $k_1\nu$ vs. V is slightly out of the total (I - V) plot area, yet the capacitive contribution is unaffected as it is determined from the enclosed (colored) area.

Fig. S11. Example for the separation of current into surface-controlled capacitive and diffusion-controlled intercalative pseudocapacitive path from CV curves measured at the scan rate 10, 25, 50 and 75 mV s^{-1} for 2.5 wt% VS_x /graphite film in three-electrode configuration for Fig. 5H.

Table S3. The k_I (slope) values determined according to Dunn's method following Equation 6.

Anodic sweep		Cathodic sweep	
Potential (V)	k_I	Potential (V)	k_I
0.008502	-0.0921	0.950317	0.0841
0.050064	-0.0158	0.901489	0.0621
0.101563	-0.0066	0.850830	0.0304
0.150635	0.0052	0.802002	0.0259
0.201965	0.0146	0.750732	0.0245
0.250885	0.0236	0.702026	-0.0095
0.302246	0.0327	0.650818	-0.0558
0.351288	0.0342	0.601685	-0.0660
0.402130	0.0212	0.550812	-0.0250
0.451141	-0.0204	0.501801	0.0353
0.500214	-0.0779	0.450317	0.0802
0.551819	-0.1283	0.401276	0.1347
0.600922	-0.1237	0.352386	0.1079
0.651947	0.0159	0.301361	-0.2826
0.700409	0.2206	0.250153	-0.3098
0.751038	0.2960	0.150116	-0.2841
0.802612	0.3150	0.101227	-0.2146
0.850830	0.2740	0.050000	-0.1066
0.902100	0.1805	0.006055	-0.0909
0.950928	0.1540		
1.000061	0.1444		

Evaluation of energy efficiency from GCD curves

Energy efficiency can be expressed as the ratio of the discharge energy to the charge energy in Equation S10.[21,22] Compared to Coulombic efficiency that considers the charge and discharge capacity (or time), energy efficiency takes into consideration the energy aspects. Hence, energy efficiency is a good alternative to evaluate the efficiency performance of a supercapacitor, especially for materials that demonstrate pseudocapacitive properties. The area under the graph of GCD curves are the charge and discharge energy, as demonstrated by Fig. S12 for the 2.5 wt% VS_x/graphite film at the current density of 2 mA cm⁻².

$$\text{Energy efficiency, } \eta_E = \frac{\text{Discharge energy, } E_{int/D}}{\text{Charge energy, } E_{int/C}} \times 100 \% \quad \text{Equation S10}$$

$$\text{where } E_{int/D} = I \int_{t(V_{max})}^{t(V_{min})} V(t) \quad \text{Equation S10a}$$

$$E_{int/C} = I \int_{t(V_{min})}^{t(V_{max})} V(t) \quad \text{Equation S10b}$$

Fig. S12. Demonstration of charge and discharge energy as the area under the graph of GCD curves for 2.5 wt% VS_x/graphite film at the current density of 2 mA cm⁻².

Table S4. Parameters of the simulated EIS circuit model.

R_s (Ω)	C_{dl} (mF)	R_{p1} (Ω)	R_{p2} (Ω)	W_d (mS. S^{0.5})	CPE (mS. sⁿ)	n
11.10	2.57	2.92	566	231	19.90	0.88

Table S5. IR drop at different current densities for 2.5 wt% VS_x/graphite film as a symmetric solid-state supercapacitor.

Current density (mA cm ⁻²)	IR drop (V)
0.5	0.050
0.8	0.080
1	0.102
3	0.289
5	0.436

Table S6. Comparison of the VS_x/graphite-PLA flexible film in capacitive performance.

Materials and composition	Synthesis procedure of VS _x	Cell type	Electrolyte	Potential window	Specific capacitance at certain scan rate/ current density	Cyclic stability	Ref.
VS ₂ /MWCNT/PVF (mass ratio 8:1:1)	Hydrothermal	Three-electrode	6 M KOH	0 – 0.4 V	33 F g ⁻¹ at 1 mA*	N/A	[23]
VS ₂ + MWCNT core-shell structure	SILAR	Symmetric SC	PVA-LiClO ₄	0 – 1.6 V	118 F g ⁻¹ at current density 2 mA cm ⁻²	93.2 % (> 5,000 CV cycles)	[24]
VS ₂ thin film	Hydrothermal	In-plane symmetric SC	BMIMBF ₄ -PVA	0.02 – 0.6 V	4.76 mF cm ⁻² *	90 % (> 1,000 cycles)	[25]
VS ₂ (V _{1.1} S ₂) nanosheet	CVD	Three-electrode	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	-0.3 – 0.6 V	860 F g ⁻¹ at scan rate 5 mV s ⁻¹	85% (> 1,000 cycles)	[26]
VS ₂ nanosheet	Hydrothermal	Three-electrode	6 M KOH	0 – 0.4 V	516.5 F g ⁻¹ at scan rate 5 mV s ⁻¹	N/A	[27]
2.5 wt% VS _x /graphite-PLA flexible self-standing film	Metal-chalcogen combustion, exfoliation by n-butyllithium	Symmetric SC, w/o ext. current collector	PVA-H ₂ SO ₄	0 – 1.0 V	123 mF cm ⁻² at current density 0.5 mA cm ⁻²	97% (> 10,000 cycles)	This work

Note 1: N/A: Not available

Note 2: *scan rate or current density was not provided in the article

Fig. S13. Ionic conductivity of the PVA/H₂SO₄ gel electrolyte used in SS-SC measured over a week.

References

- [1] S. Trasatti, O.A. Petrii, Real surface area measurements in electrochemistry, *Pure Appl. Chem.* 63 (1991) 711–734. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728\(92\)80162-W](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-0728(92)80162-W).
- [2] C.C.L. McCrory, S. Jung, J.C. Peters, T.F. Jaramillo, Benchmarking heterogeneous electrocatalysts for the oxygen evolution reaction, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 135 (2013) 16977–16987. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja407115p>.
- [3] P.L. Taberna, P. Simon, J.F. Fauvarque, Electrochemical characteristics and impedance spectroscopy studies of carbon-carbon supercapacitors, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* 150 (2003) A292. <https://doi.org/10.1149/1.1543948>.
- [4] G. Ma, M. Dong, K. Sun, E. Feng, H. Peng, Z. Lei, A redox mediator doped gel polymer as an electrolyte and separator for a high performance solid state supercapacitor, *J. Mater. Chem. A.* 3 (2015) 4035–4041. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4TA06322H>.
- [5] H. Liang, H. Shi, D. Zhang, F. Ming, R. Wang, J. Zhuo, Z. Wang, Solution growth of vertical VS₂ nanoplate arrays for electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution, *Chem. Mater.* 28 (2016) 5587–5591. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.6b01963>.
- [6] X. Chia, A. Ambrosi, P. Lazar, Z. Sofer, M. Pumera, Electrocatalysis of layered Group 5 metallic transition metal dichalcogenides (MX₂, M = V, Nb, and Ta; X = S, Se, and Te), *J. Mater. Chem. A.* 4 (2016) 14241–14253. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c6ta05110c>.
- [7] Y. Wang, Z. Sofer, J. Luxa, M. Pumera, Lithium exfoliated vanadium dichalcogenides (VS₂, VSe₂, VTe₂) exhibit dramatically different properties from their bulk counterparts, *Adv. Mater. Interfaces.* 3 (2016) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.201600433>.
- [8] J. Zhang, C. Zhang, Z. Wang, J. Zhu, Z. Wen, X. Zhao, X. Zhang, J. Xu, Z. Lu, Synergistic interlayer and defect engineering in VS₂ nanosheets toward efficient electrocatalytic hydrogen evolution reaction, *Small.* 14 (2018) 1703098. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smll.201703098>.

- [9] J. Yuan, J. Wu, W.J. Hardy, P. Loya, M. Lou, Y. Yang, S. Najmaei, M. Jiang, F. Qin, K. Keyshar, H. Ji, W. Gao, J. Bao, J. Kono, D. Natelson, P.M. Ajayan, J. Lou, Facile synthesis of single crystal vanadium disulfide nanosheets by chemical vapor deposition for efficient hydrogen evolution reaction, *Adv. Mater.* 27 (2015) 5605–5609. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201502075>.
- [10] P. Mohan, J. Yang, A. Jena, H. Suk Shin, VS₂/rGO hybrid nanosheets prepared by annealing of VS₄/rGO, *J. Solid State Chem.* 224 (2015) 82–87. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jssc.2014.06.031>.
- [11] Y. Qu, M. Shao, Y. Shao, M. Yang, J. Xu, C.T. Kwok, X. Shi, Z. Lu, H. Pan, Ultra-high electrocatalytic activity of VS₂ nanoflowers for efficient hydrogen evolution reaction, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 5 (2017) 15080–15086. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7TA03172F>.
- [12] J.K. Das, A.K. Samantara, A.K. Nayak, D. Pradhan, J.N. Behera, VS₂: An efficient catalyst for an electrochemical hydrogen evolution reaction in an acidic medium, *Dalt. Trans.* 47 (2018) 13792–13799. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C8DT02547A>.
- [13] S. Ng, R. Zazpe, J. Rodriguez-Pereira, J. Michalička, J.M. Macak, M. Pumera, Atomic layer deposition of photoelectrocatalytic material on 3D-printed nanocarbon structures, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 9 (2021) 11405–11414. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1TA01467F>.
- [14] K. Ghosh, S. Ng, C. Iffelsberger, M. Pumera, 2D MoS₂/carbon/polylactic acid filament for 3D printing: Photo and electrochemical energy conversion and storage, *Appl. Mater. Today* 26 (2022) 101301. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmt.2021.101301>.
- [15] Y. Qi, Q. Xu, Y. Wang, B. Yan, Y. Ren, Z. Chen, CO₂-induced phase engineering: protocol for enhanced photoelectrocatalytic performance of 2D MoS₂ Nanosheets, *ACS Nano* 10 (2016) 2903–2909. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nano.6b00001>.
- [16] M. Patel, M. Kumar, J. Kim, Y.K. Kim, Photocurrent enhancement by a rapid thermal treatment of nanodisk-shaped SnS photocathodes, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* 8 (2017) 6099–6105. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcclett.7b02998>.
- [17] J. Luo, S.D. Tilley, L. Steier, M. Schreier, M.T. Mayer, H.J. Fan, M. Grätzel, Solution transformation of Cu₂O into CuInS₂ for solar water splitting, *Nano Lett.* 15 (2015) 1395–1402. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl504746b>.
- [18] J. Park, W. Yang, J. Tan, H. Lee, J.W. Yun, S.G. Shim, Y.S. Park, J. Moon, Hierarchical nanorod-derived bilayer strategy to enhance the photocurrent density of Sb₂Se₃ photocathodes for photoelectrochemical water splitting, *ACS Energy Lett.* 5 (2020) 136–145. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.9b02486>.
- [19] V. Augustyn, J. Come, M.A. Lowe, J.W. Kim, P.-L. Taberna, S.H. Tolbert, H.D. Abruña, P. Simon, B. Dunn, High-rate electrochemical energy storage through Li⁺ intercalation pseudocapacitance, *Nat. Mater.* 12 (2013) 518–522. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat3601>.
- [20] J. Wang, J. Polleux, J. Lim, B. Dunn, Pseudocapacitive contributions to electrochemical energy storage in TiO₂ (anatase) nanoparticles, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 111 (2007) 14925–14931. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp074464w>.
- [21] A. Laheäär, P. Przygocki, Q. Abbas, F. Béguin, Appropriate methods for evaluating the

- efficiency and capacitive behavior of different types of supercapacitors, *Electrochem. Commun.* 60 (2015) 21–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.elecom.2015.07.022>.
- [22] V.K. Mariappan, K. Krishnamoorthy, P. Pazhamalai, S. Sahoo, D. Kesavan, S. Kim, Two dimensional farnatinite sheets decorated on reduced graphene oxide: A novel electrode for high performance supercapacitors, *J. Power Sources.* 433 (2019) 126648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2019.05.056>.
- [23] E. Meyer, A. Bede, D. Mutukwa, R. Taziwa, N. Zingwe, Optimization, and analysis of carbon supported VS₂ nanocomposites as potential electrodes in supercapacitors, *J. Energy Storage.* 27 (2020) 101074. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2019.101074>.
- [24] B. Pandit, S.S. Karade, B.R. Sankapal, Hexagonal VS₂ anchored MWCNTs: First approach to design flexible solid-state symmetric supercapacitor device, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces.* 9 (2017) 44880–44891. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b13908>.
- [25] J. Feng, X. Sun, C. Wu, L. Peng, C. Lin, S. Hu, J. Yang, Y. Xie, Metallic few-layered VS₂ ultrathin nanosheets: High two-dimensional conductivity for in-plane supercapacitors, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 133 (2011) 17832–17838. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja207176c>.
- [26] Q. Ji, C. Li, J. Wang, J. Niu, Y. Gong, Z. Zhang, Q. Fang, Y. Zhang, J. Shi, L. Liao, X. Wu, L. Gu, Z. Liu, Y. Zhang, Metallic vanadium disulfide nanosheets as a platform material for multifunctional electrode applications, *Nano Lett.* 17 (2017) 4908–4916. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.7b01914>.
- [27] M.N. Rantho, M.J. Madito, F.O. Ochai-Ejeh, N. Manyala, Asymmetric supercapacitor based on vanadium disulfide nanosheets as a cathode and carbonized iron cations adsorbed onto polyaniline as an anode, *Electrochim. Acta.* 260 (2018) 11–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2017.11.074>.